
Supplement for “Causal Transfer for Imitation Learning and Decision Making under Sensor-shift”

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1 Proofs for Section 6 of the main paper

Proof for Proposition 1 of the main paper. In this proof, let Y be shorthand for Y_S . First observe that

$$\Sigma_{ZY} = \Sigma_{Z(FX+N)} = \Sigma_{ZX}F^T + \Sigma_{ZN} = \Sigma_{ZX}F^T \quad (1)$$

$$\Sigma_{AY} = \Sigma_{A(FX+N)} = \Sigma_{AX}F^T + \Sigma_{AN} = \Sigma_{AX}F^T \quad (2)$$

$$\Sigma_{YY} = \Sigma_{(FX+N)(FX+N)} = F\Sigma_{XX}F^T + \Sigma_{NN}, \quad (3)$$

due to the independence of N to the other variables.

Due to F invertible

$$\Sigma_{ZX} = \Sigma_{ZY}(F^T)^{-1} \quad (4)$$

$$\Sigma_{AX} = \Sigma_{AY}(F^T)^{-1} \quad (5)$$

$$\Sigma_{XX} = F^{-1}(\Sigma_{YY} - \Sigma_{NN})(F^T)^{-1}. \quad (6)$$

Let

$$Q := \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & F \end{bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

As usual, Eq. 4 implies

$$(D, E) = (\Sigma_{ZA}, \Sigma_{ZX}) \begin{bmatrix} \Sigma_{AA} & \Sigma_{AX} \\ \Sigma_{XA} & \Sigma_{XX} \end{bmatrix}^{-1} \quad (8)$$

$$= (\Sigma_{ZA}, \Sigma_{ZY}(F^T)^{-1}) \begin{bmatrix} \Sigma_{AA} & \Sigma_{AY}(F^T)^{-1} \\ F^{-1}\Sigma_{YA} & F^{-1}(\Sigma_{YY} - \Sigma_{NN})(F^T)^{-1} \end{bmatrix}^{-1} \quad (9)$$

$$= (\Sigma_{ZA}, \Sigma_{ZY}(F^T)^{-1}) \left(Q^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} \Sigma_{AA} & \Sigma_{AX} \\ \Sigma_{XA} & \Sigma_{XX} - \Sigma_{NN} \end{bmatrix} (Q^T)^{-1} \right)^{-1} \quad (10)$$

$$= (\Sigma_{ZA}, \Sigma_{ZY}(F^T)^{-1}) Q^T \begin{bmatrix} \Sigma_{AA} & \Sigma_{AY} \\ \Sigma_{YA} & \Sigma_{YY} - \Sigma_{NN} \end{bmatrix}^{-1} Q \quad (11)$$

$$= (\Sigma_{ZA}, \Sigma_{ZY}) \begin{bmatrix} S_1^{-1} & -S_1^{-1}\Sigma_{AY}(\Sigma_{YY} - \Sigma_{NN})^{-1} \\ -(\Sigma_{YY} - \Sigma_{NN})^{-1}\Sigma_{YA}S_1^{-1} & S_2^{-1} \end{bmatrix} Q \quad (12)$$

$$= (\Sigma_{ZA}S_1^{-1} - \Sigma_{ZY}(\Sigma_{YY} - \Sigma_{NN})^{-1}\Sigma_{YA}S_1^{-1} \quad (13)$$

$$(-\Sigma_{ZA}S_1^{-1}\Sigma_{AY}(\Sigma_{YY} - \Sigma_{NN})^{-1} + \Sigma_{ZY}S_2^{-1})F), \quad (14)$$

where, as usual, the Schur complements are defined as

$$S_1 := \Sigma_{AA} - \Sigma_{AY}(\Sigma_{YY} - \Sigma_{NN})^{-1}\Sigma_{YA}, \quad (15)$$

$$S_2 := \Sigma_{YY} - \Sigma_{NN} - \Sigma_{YA}\Sigma_{AA}^{-1}\Sigma_{AY}. \quad (16)$$

□

Proof of Proposition 2 of the main paper. Recall that we allow variables to be discrete or continuous, where in the continuous case we assumed that the joint probability has a density, and this density has support everywhere. We have

$$D(P_S(Z|X, A) || \tilde{P}(Z|X, A)) \quad (17)$$

$$= \int_{x,a,z} p(z|x, a)p_S(x, a) \left(-\log \frac{\int_{y_S} p_S(z|y_S, A)p(y_S|x)}{P(z|x, a)} \right) \quad (18)$$

$$= \int_{x,a,z} p(z|x, a)p_S(x, a) \left(-\log \int_{y_S} p(y_S|x) \frac{p_S(z|y_S, a)}{p(z|x, a)} \right) \quad (19)$$

$$\leq \int_{x,a,z} p(z|x, a)p_S(x, a) \left(-\int_{y_S} p(y_S|x) \log \frac{p_S(z|y_S, a)}{p(z|x, a)} \right) \quad (20)$$

$$= - \int_{x,a,z} p(z|x, a)p_S(x, a) \int_{y_S} p(y_S|x) \log \frac{p_S(z|y_S, a)}{p(z|x, a)} \quad (21)$$

$$= - \int_{x,a,z} p(z|x, a)p_S(x, a) \int_{y_S: p(y_S, x) > 0} p(y_S|x) \log \frac{p_S(z|y_S, a)}{p_S(z|x, y_S, a)} \quad (22)$$

$$= - \int_{x,a,z} \int_{y_S: p(y_S, x) > 0} p(z|x, y_S, a)p_S(x, a)p(y_S|x, a) \log \frac{p_S(z|y_S, a)}{p_S(z|x, y_S, a)} \quad (23)$$

$$= - \int_{x,a,z} \int_{y_S: p(y_S, x) > 0} p(z|x, y_S, a)p_S(y_S, x, a) \log \frac{p_S(z|y_S, a)}{p_S(z|x, y_S, a)} \quad (24)$$

$$= - \int_{x,a,z} \int_{y_S: p(y_S, x) > 0} p(z, x|y_S, a)p_S(y_S, a) \log \frac{p_S(z|y_S, a)p_S(x|y_S, a)}{p_S(z, x|y_S, a)}, \quad (25)$$

$$(26)$$

where

- in Eq. 20 we used Jensen's inequality;
- Eq. 22 and 23 we used conditional independences that follow from the causal DAG (plus Markov assumption);

Additionally, in the discrete case we have

$$I_S(Z : X|Y_S, A) = H_S(X|Y_S, A) - H_S(X|Z, Y_S, A) \quad (27)$$

$$\leq H_S(X|Y_S) \quad (28)$$

$$\leq \max_{P'(X)} H_{X \sim P'(X)}(X|Y_S). \quad (29)$$

□

2 Proofs for Section 7 of the main paper

Proof of Proposition 3 of the main paper. We have

$$\begin{aligned} D\left(P_T(A, Z|X) \parallel P_S(A, Z|X)\right) &= \int_{a,z,x} P_T(a, z|x) P_T(x) \log \frac{P_T(a, z|x)}{P_S(a, z|x)} \\ &= \int_{a,x} P_T(a|x) P_T(x) \log \frac{P_T(a|x)}{P_S(a|x)} = \int_{a,x} P_T(a|x) P_T(x) \log \frac{\int_{y_T} \pi_T(a|y_T) P(y_T|x)}{\int_{y_D} \pi_D(a|y_D) P(y_D|x)}. \end{aligned}$$

Because $P_S(Y_D|X) = P_T(Y_T|X)$ and $Y_T = Y_D$, by choosing π_T to be the same as π_D , the above KL-divergence becomes zero. \square

Proof of Proposition 4 of the main paper. We have

$$\begin{aligned} D(\pi_D(A|Y_D) \parallel \tilde{\pi}_T^{(1)}(A|Y_D)) &= \int_{y,a} P_S(Y_D = y, a) \log \frac{P_S(a|Y_D = y)}{\int_{y'} P_S(a|Y_S = y') P_S(Y_S = y'|y)} \\ &\leq \int_{y,a,y'} P_S(y, a) P_S(y'|y) \log \frac{P_S(a|y)}{P_S(a|y')} = \int_{y,a,y'} P_S(y, a, y') \log \frac{P_S(a|y, y')}{P_S(a|y')} = I_S(A; Y_D|Y_S). \end{aligned}$$

Here, we used the convexity of $-\log(\cdot)$ and the fact that Y_S and A are d-separated by Y_D . \square

Proof of Proposition 5 of the main paper. We have

$$\begin{aligned} D\left(P_T(A, Z|X) \parallel P_S(A, Z|X)\right) &= \int_{a,x} P_T(a|x) P_T(x) \log \frac{\int_y \tilde{\pi}_T^{(1)}(a|y) P(y|x)}{\int_y \pi_D(a|y) P(y|x)} \\ &\leq \int_{a,x,y} P_T(a|x) P_T(x) \frac{\tilde{\pi}_T^{(1)}(a|y) P(y|x)}{\int_{y'} \tilde{\pi}_T^{(1)}(a|y') P(y'|x)} \log \frac{\tilde{\pi}_T^{(1)}(a|y)}{\pi_D(a|y)} \\ &= \int_{a,y} \tilde{\pi}_T(a|y) P_T(y) \log \frac{\tilde{\pi}_T^{(1)}(a|y)}{\pi_D(a|y)} = D(\tilde{\pi}_T^{(1)} \parallel \pi_D). \end{aligned}$$

The above inequality is due to the log-sum inequality. \square

2.1 Derivation of Case 2 and Case 3 in Section 7 of the main paper

Herein, we show the second case. The third case can be obtained similarly. Due to the convexity of $x \log x$ and concavity of $\log x$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} D\left(p_T(A, Z|X) \parallel p_S(A, Z|X)\right) &\leq \int_{a,x} p_T(a|x) p_T(x) \int_{y_T} \frac{\pi_T(a|y_T) P(y_T|x)}{p_T(a|x)} \log \pi_T(a|y_T) \\ &\quad - \int_{a,x} p_T(a|x) p_T(x) \int_{y_S} p_S(y_S|x) \log p_S(a|y_S) \\ &= \int_{a,y_T,y_S} \pi_T(a|y_T) p(y_S, y_T) \left[\log \pi_T(a|y_T) - \log p_S(a|y_S) \right]. \end{aligned} \tag{30}$$

Minimizing (30) will lead to the following policy for the imitator.

$$\pi_T^* := \arg \min_{\pi_T} \int_{a,y_T,y_S} \pi_T(a|y_T) p(y_S, y_T) \left[\log \pi_T(a|y_T) - \log p_S(a|y_S) \right].$$

The Lagrangian function of this problem will be

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{a, y_T, y_S} \pi_T(a|y_T) p(y_S, y_T) \left[\log \pi_T(a|y_T) - \log p_S(a|y_S) \right] - \sum_{y_T} \lambda_{y_T} \left(\sum_a \pi_T(a|y_T) - 1 \right) \\ & - \sum_{a, y_T} \beta_{a, y_T} \pi_T(a|y_T), \end{aligned}$$

for positive β_{a, y_T} . Taking the derivative of the above Lagrangian with respect to $\{\pi_T(a|y_T)\}$ will lead to the following set of equations

$$P(y_T) \log \pi_T(a|y_T) - \lambda_{y_T} = \beta_{a, y_T} + \sum_{y_S} P(y_S, y_T) \log p_S(a|y_S) - P(y_T), \quad \forall a, y_T. \quad (31)$$

Considering

$$\begin{aligned} \beta_{a, y_T} &= P(y_T), \quad \lambda_{y_T} = -P(y_T) \log Z_{y_T}, \\ \pi_T(a|y_T) &= \frac{\exp\left(\sum_{y_S} P(y_S|y_T) \log p_S(a|y_S)\right)}{Z_{y_T}}, \end{aligned}$$

where Z_{y_T} is the normalization factor, will solve (31). Since in the second case, Y_D and Y_S are the same, the imitator can estimate $\pi_D(a|y_S)$ using his observation from the source domain.

In **Case three**, by following the same steps as in (30), one can obtain the next upper bound for Equation 6 of the main paper,

$$\arg \min_{\pi_T} \sum_{a, y_T, x} \pi_T(a|y_T) P(x, y_T) \left[\log \pi_T(a|y_T) - \log p_S(a|x) \right]. \quad (32)$$

Note that $p_S(a|x)$ is not known to the imitator. Hence, we minimize an objective function in which $p_S(a|x)$ is substituted by its proxy that is $\tilde{p}(a|x) := \sum_{y_S} p_S(a|y_S) p_S(y_S|x)$.

Similar to the previous case, the solution to (32) will be

$$\pi_T(a|y_T) = \frac{\exp\left(\sum_x P(x|y_T) \log \tilde{p}(a|x)\right)}{\hat{Z}_{y_T}}, \quad (33)$$

where \hat{Z}_{y_T} denotes the normalization factor.

Proof of Proposition 6 of the main paper. Plugging the policy of Case two into (30) will imply $-\sum_{y_T} P(y_T) \log Z_{y_T}$. Next, we show that

$$0 \leq -\sum_{y_T} P(y_T) \log Z_{y_T} \leq -\sum_{a', y_S, x} p_T(a', x) p_S(y_S|x) \log p_S(a'|y_S).$$

To show the first inequality, we prove that $Z_{y_T} \leq 1$ for every y_T . Let us define

$$\begin{aligned} \psi(\theta) &= \sum_a \prod_{y_S} \pi_D(a|y_S)^{\theta_{y_S}} - 1. \\ g(t) &= \psi(\theta' + t\theta). \end{aligned}$$

Since $g(t)$ is convex, so does ψ . On the other hand, for any vertex point (i.e., $\theta_{y_S} = 1$ for exactly one y_S and zero, otherwise) $\psi(\theta_{y_S}) = 0$. Thus, $\psi(\theta) \leq 0$ for all θ such that $\sum_{y_S} \theta_{y_S} = 1$. Hence, we

have $Z_{y_T} = \psi([p(y_S|y_T)]) + 1 \leq 1$. To show the second inequality, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
& - \sum_{y_T} p(y_T) \log Z_{y_T} = - \sum_{y_T} p(y_T) \log \sum_a \exp\left(\sum_{y_S} p(y_S|y_T) \log p_S(a|y_S)\right) \\
& = - \sum_{y_T} p(y_T) \log \sum_a \frac{\pi_T(a|y_T)}{\pi_T(a|y_T)} \exp\left(\sum_{y_S} p(y_S|y_T) \log p_S(a|y_S)\right) \\
& \leq - \sum_{y_T} \sum_a p_T(y_T) \pi_T(a|y_T) \left[\log \frac{1}{\pi_T(a|y_T)} \exp\left(\sum_{y_S} p(y_S|y_T) \log p_S(a|y_S)\right) \right] \\
& = - \sum_{a, y_T} p_T(a, y_T) \left[\log \frac{1}{\pi_T(a|y_T)} + \sum_{y_S} p(y_S|y_T) \log p_S(a|y_S) \right] \\
& = \sum_{a, y_T} \sum_{y_S} p(y_S|y_T) p_T(a, y_T) \log \frac{\pi_T(a|y_T)}{p_S(a|y_S)}.
\end{aligned}$$

□

3 Setup in Section 8.2 of the main paper

We formulated the imitation learning task in the experiments section as a linear programming problem,

$$\begin{aligned}
& \min_x c^T x \\
& s.t. \quad 0 \leq x_{a,y} \leq 1, \forall a, y, \\
& P_S(a, y_S) = \sum_y P_S(y_S|y_D = y) x_{a,y}, \forall a, y_S,
\end{aligned}$$

where $x_{a,y} := P_S(a, y_D = y)$. The second condition is to ensure that the policy satisfies the observational equations, i.e., Equation (7) of the main paper. In particular, for our experiment, we used the following setting,

$$\begin{aligned}
& y_D = (v_o, b_o), \quad v_o \in \{40, 45, \dots, 60\}, \quad b_o \in \{0, 1\}, \\
& c_{a, v_o, b_o} = \begin{cases} 1 & a = -1, b_o = 0 \\ 1 & a = 1, b_o = 1 \\ 0 & o.w. \end{cases}
\end{aligned}$$

Minimizing the objective function $c^T x$ gives us a solution that does not break ($a = -1$) when the indicator of the other vehicle is off ($b_o = 0$) and does not accelerate when the indicator is on.